

WORK-PACKAGE 1

Repository of European/international
population-based, cohorts, patients' cohorts,
control trials, ordered by region

D1.2

SYNCHROS
PUBLIC REPOSITORY
<https://repository.synchros.eu>

SYnergies for Cohorts in Health: integrating
the Role of all Stakeholders

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report contains a concise description of the online repository of the SYNCHROS project (Deliverable 1.2).

Intended readers and users of this document are project team members who are involved in the project work, for instance as authors of deliverables, WP-leaders, authors of web-articles, bloggers or anyone who is in charge of external communication and dissemination.

The document contains the following information:

- Description of overall structure and content of the repository.
- Technical characteristics of the repository construction.
- Details on how to use the data management site.
- An overview of the public repository.

1. INTRODUCTION

The SYNCHROS project aims to establish a sustainable European strategy for the development of the next generation of integrated population, patient and clinical trial cohorts, thereby contributing to an international strategic agenda for enhanced coordination of cohorts globally.

In order to achieve this objective, SYNCHROS has mapped the cohort landscape in Europe and large international initiatives, collected the best methods for integrating cohort data, identified solutions for addressing practical, ethical and legal challenges in integrating data across patient, clinical trial and population cohorts, and evaluated the use of emerging and new data collection technologies and types of data.

In accordance with Deliverable 1.3 and 1.4, the data of 136 initiatives (55 initiatives integrate population cohorts, 44 initiatives of patients' cohorts, 22 clinical trials and 15 initiatives that integrate new exposures and health risk) have been collected. The general inclusion criteria for the initiatives mapping were:

- Initiatives/Cohorts/Meta-analyses published in English.
- Published since 2000.
- Available data (public or under request)

The information collected for the mapping is being included in a public online repository. The repository consists of individual descriptions of a great amount of European and international initiatives of harmonized and their integrated cohorts.

This report contains a detailed description of the public repository of the SYNCHROS project, including the technical aspects of the development and its functioning.

Intended readers and users of this document are project team members who are involved in the project work, for instance as authors of deliverables, WP-leaders, or anyone who is in charge of external communication and dissemination.

2. THE REPOSITORY

2.1 Overview

The repository offers a public collection of information about the main European and international efforts to harmonise and integrate cohort data including details about harmonisation and integration methodology, communication technologies used in cohorts and exposure and health risk cohorts.

It represents the digital platform for general public information compiled of European and international initiatives and cohorts mapped by WP1, WP2 and WP4 of the SYNCHROS project.

The SYNCHROS Repository has been developed with the objective of having a long-term solution that can continuously be enriched, even after the project has ended.

2.2 Technical characteristics of the repository.synchros.eu

The software tools that have been used are the ones provided by the OBiBa group (www.obiba.org). Epigeny, partner of the SYNCHROS project, is responsible for the development and maintenance of the OBiBa software suite source code and as such has led the adaptation of the software for SYNCHROS' needs and their deployment on the infrastructure of Parc Sanitari Sant Joan de Déu (PSSJD – Coordinator of SYNCHROS).

2.2.1 Server

The SYNCHROS Repository is hosted on a server at PSSJD. The technical specifications of this virtual machine server are:

- 4 vCPU
- 8 GB RAM memory
- 50 GB Sata Hard disk
- Ubuntu server 18.10 LTS

This server is accessible through a Virtual Private Network and using secure shell connections.

2.2.2 Software applications

The OBiBa solution is composed of two software applications:

- **Mica**, the data catalog application (www.obiba.org/pages/products/mica/)
- **Agate**, the user management application (www.obiba.org/pages/products/agate/)

These software applications and required adaptations have been developed to meet two objectives:

- Simplification of the deployment and configuration in order to facilitate the long-term maintenance of the SYNCHROS Repository,

- Definition of additional settings for SYNCHROS' needs, being the ability to define a catalogue of *Networks* (a.k.a. *Initiatives*) and *Studies* only (**Mica** is primarily designed for making a data web portal, i.e. cataloguing networks/studies with datasets and variables).

Additional software applications that have been installed:

- **Apache** web server, which is the entry point for accessing the OBiBa applications,
- **Docker** application container software, to facilitate the deployment and the upgrades of software applications,
- **MongoDB**, the database server used by Mica and Agate.

2.3 Repository structure of content

The SYNCHROS Repository can be accessed via the SYNCHROS project website or the following URL: repository.synchros.eu.

The page layout and styling of these web applications have been adapted to match the one of the main SYNCHROS website for a seamless transition from one to the other.

Figure 1. Screenshot of the homepage of the repository.

The content is structured in three public menu-accesses on the top of the page, on the right of the SYNCHROS logo (Home, Repository and About) and a search button. The SYNCHROS logo on the top left side is a link to the main website of the project (<https://synchros.eu>). At the bottom right of the homepage, the blue padlock leads to the administration-section for internal purposes, where the published and publishable information can be managed only by authorized members.

- **Home:** Access to the homepage of the repository (under construction) where the repository aim is described. The content of the homepage is still under construction.

- **Repository:** A drop-down menu is displayed with two options: Initiatives and Studies. These two sections lead to the lists of the initiatives and studies, respectively.

Figure 2. Image of the dropdown repository menu deployed.

- **About:** This access contains relevant information about the content of the repository. A drop-down menu is displayed with three options: Methodology, Bibliography and Contacts. The Methodology menu contains a detailed description of the terms used in the methodology section of the initiatives; The Bibliography menu contains the search sources for methodology terms and Contacts brings an email of contact to the SYNCHROS team for any queries and questions.

Figure 3. Image of the dropdown about menu deployed and content of the “methodology” menu.

The repository is online since March 15th, 2020. Adjustments and improvements can be made, if required, following experiences after going online.

The content will be updated with the information collected about initiatives and cohorts throughout the duration of the project. The aim is to maintain the repository up-to-date after the project ends. However, this will also depend on available resources in terms of funding.

2.4 Administration Section

2.4.1 Administration section access: Agate and Mica.

The user management application is located at: <https://agate.synchros.eu>.

The **Agate** application is for internal usage only (to define administrators and users responsible for content edition and publication).

The administration section is located at: <https://repository.synchros.eu/admin>. This site hosts the **Mica** data management portal. For accessing the administration site of the repository, an account (user and password) provided by EPIGENY through Agate is required.

Figure 4. Login to Mica site screenshot.

2.4.2 Administration section structure: Mica

The **Mica** application exposes the following pages:

- *Home*, the repository landing page, with a link to the SYNCHROS main website (synchros.eu),
- *Initiatives*, the list of initiatives page and the associated pages for each of the items,
- *Studies*, the list of studies and the associated pages for each of the items,
- *Search*, which allows to combine search criteria to find initiatives and studies,
- *Administration*, the **Mica's** content administration interface, for entering the initiatives and the studies and publishing them.

Figure 5. Homepage of Mica site.

Mica is a powerful application with an extensible data model. The data model definition is used in the following contexts:

- **Data entry**, a form is generated to capture the Initiative and Study items. In order to ensure the data quality, the form includes rich input widgets, field dependencies conditions, validations and field descriptions.
- **Data display**, each published item page can be fully configured by defining a page template that matches the data model,
- **Data search**, the search criteria are defined by taxonomies that are designed according to the data model.

The development of the different configuration files that implement the SYNCHROS data model are available at github.com/epigeny/synchros.

2.4.3 Instructions to upload information

Network:

1. To add a new network to the repository just click on the “Network” button of the top menu and then click the “+Add Network” blue button.

Figure 6 Networks general editing site screenshot.

2. A form page is displayed to be completed with the information about initiatives and networks previously collected. This form contains fields about general information of the initiative as well as the methodology for harmonization and integration used.

Networks / New Network

Logo

Choose file

General Information

Name

Acronym

Description

B I H | " | | | | | | | | |

Website

Data entry date

Date at which information was collected

Year created

Types of cohorts

- Population cohort
- Patient/disease cohort
- Clinical trial

Criteria of cohort's to be included

Socio-environmental context

- Air pollution
- Climate change
- Environmental hazards
- Short-half-life chemicals
- Urbanization
- Work-related stress
- Work/life balance
- Migration
- VNPs
- Internet use
- Social media use
- Gaming online
- Gaming offline
- Other
- NA

Countries

Region

Setting

- Local/regional
- National
- International

Funding

Number of participants

Total

With harmonized data

Age range of the samples

Minimum age

Maximum age

Methodology for harmonization and integration

Strategy of harmonization

ex-ante
 ex-post
 NA

Type of harmonization

Prospective
 Retrospective
 NA

Software

Analyses

Meta-analyses
 Pooled analyses
 Federated analyses
 Other
 NA

Data processing methods

Supplementary information

Add a comment to describe the changes.

Number of cohorts

Total

With harmonized data

Will more cohorts be harmonized?

Yes No

Number of harmonized variables (max.)

Access

Availability of metadata

Availability of individual data

Figure 7. Screenshot of the Network's form.

- Once the fields are completed, the information is saved by clicking the blue button "Save" at the end of the form.
- All initiatives are listed at the "Network" Menu. This list shows whether the network is already published in the public repository site, the status and the pencil icon allows to edit the information.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL repository.synchros.eu. The navigation bar includes 'Synchros', 'Networks', 'Individual Studies', 'Files', 'Administration', 'Help', and a user profile 'Desiree Gutierrez Marin'. The main content area is titled 'Networks' and features a '+ Add Network' button and a search bar. Below is a table listing various networks with columns for ID, Acronym, Name, Published, Status, and Actions.

ID	Acronym	Name	Published	Status	Actions
agricoh	AGRICOH	A consortium of agricultural cohort studies	★	Draft	
athlos	ATHLOS	Ageing Trajectories of Health: Longitudinal Opportunities and Synergies	☆	Draft	
biomarcare	BiomarCaRE	Biomarker for Cardiovascular Risk Assessment across Europe	★	Draft	
high-risk-myocardial-infarction-database-initiative	High-Risk Myocardial Infarction Database Initiative	High-Risk Myocardial Infarction Database Initiative	★ 1	Draft	
igems	IGEMS	Interplay of Genes and Environment across Multiple Studies	★	Draft	
ihcc	IHCC	International HundredK+ Cohorts Consortium	★	Draft	
nci	NCI	National Cancer Institute Cohort Consortium	★	Draft	

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Figure 8. Screenshot of the Network's list.

Study:

1. To add a new study to the repository just click on the “Individual Studies” button of the top menu and then click the “+Add Study” blue button.

Figure 8. Screenshot of the studies general editing site.

2. A form page is displayed to be fulfilled with the information about initiatives and networks previously collected. This form contains fields about general information of the individual study, the study design and the published marker paper.

Synchronos Networks Individual Studies Files
Administration Help Desiree Gutierrez Marin

Individual Studies / New Study

Logo

General Information

Name

Official study name.

Acronym

Acronym of the study.

Opal Server

URL of the opal server for this study (if different from the default one).

Objectives

B I H " ☰ 🔗 🖨️ 📄 👁️

Main objectives of the study.

License Info. This model (version 1.1.3) was released by Maelstrom Research under the Creative Commons License with Non Commercial and No Derivatives constraints.

Start Year

End Year

Website

Funding

Supplementary Information

General Design

Study Design

- Population cohort
- Patients' cohort
- Clinical trial cohort
- Case-control
- Case only
- Cross-sectional
- Clinical trial
- Other

The design of an observational or experimental study (e.g. cohort, case control).

Sources of Recruitment

- Individuals
- Families
- Other

Type of participants (e.g. individuals, families) targeted for recruitment by the study.

Number of participants

Number of participants

No Limit

Number of participants with biosamples

No Limit

Supplementary information about number of participants

Follow Up

General information on follow up (profile, frequency).

Supplementary Information

Access

General Information

Availability of data and biosamples

Data Yes No N/A

Biosamples Yes No N/A

Other Yes No N/A

Availability of access information

On the study website

By contacting the study representative

Marker Paper

Pubmed ID

Figure 10. Screenshot of the Study's form.

- Once the fields are completed, the information is saved by clicking the blue button “Save” at the end of the form.
- All initiatives are listed at the “Network” Menu. This list shows whether the network is already published in the public repository site, the status and and the pencil icon allows to edit the information.

ID	Acronym	Name	Published	Status	Actions
10_66	en 10/66	en The 10/66 Dementia Research Group Population-Based Cohort Study	☆	Draft	
alsas	en ALSA	en Australian Longitudinal Study of Aging	☆	Draft	
attica	en ATTICA	en The ATTICA Study	☆	Draft	
charls	en CHARLS	en The China Health and Retirement Longitudinal Study	☆	Draft	
courage	en COURAGE	en Collaborative Research on Ageing in Europe	☆	Draft	
elsa	en ELSA	en English Longitudinal Study of Ageing	☆	Draft	
enrica	en ENRICA	en Seniors-ENRICA	☆	Draft	
h2000_11	en H2000/11	en Health 2000/2011	☆	Draft	
haplee	en HAPIEE	en The Health, Alcohol and Psychosocial factors in Eastern Europe Study	☆	Draft	
hrs	en HRS	en Health and Retirement Survey	☆	Draft	
jstar	en JSTAR	en Japanese Study of Aging and Retirement	☆	Draft	
klosa	en KLOSA	en The Korean Longitudinal Study of Ageing	☆	Draft	
lasi	en LASI	en The Longitudinal Aging Study in India	☆	Draft	
mhas	en MHAS	en The Mexican Health and Aging Study	☆	Draft	

Figure 11. Screenshot of the Individual studies’ list.

2.4.4 How to publish

The information uploaded to Mica is hidden until explicitly published. To publish a new network or study just click the “*Publish” blue button at the top right side of the final form. This action allows to show the information in the repository site. The information unpublished remains stored in Mica until published.

Figure 12. Location of the “Publish” button of a network example.

2.5 Repository Public view

To access the Initiatives and Studies lists, a menu with two options is displayed by clicking the “Repository” option (see figure 2).

For both options, initiatives and studies, a list of the published content is shown.

Figure 13. Published initiatives list – icon view

Figure 14. Published initiatives list- list view.

Figure 15. Published studies list- icon view.

Figure 16. Published studies list- list view.

Click on the acronym of an initiative or study to consult the information provided.

Ageing Trajectories of Health: Longitudinal Opportunities and Synergies

ATHLOS

Studies
18

The objective of the ATHLOS Project is to achieve a better understanding of ageing by identifying patterns of healthy ageing pathways or trajectories, the determinants of those patterns, the critical points in time when changes in trajectories are produced, and to propose timely clinical and public health interventions to optimize healthy ageing. Moreover, a new definition of 'old age' based on many characteristics rather than just the classical chronological definition of age will be used for calculating projections in each specific population and guide policy recommendations. To do so, the Consortium will create a harmonised dataset with over 400,000 individuals collated from existing longitudinal studies of ageing and including information on physical and mental health, biomarkers, life style habits, social environment and participation, among others.

ATHLOS is a five-year project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement number 635316.

The Consortium is coordinated by Dr Josep Maria Haro (Parc Sanitari Sant Joan de Déu) and consists of 14 partners from 11 European countries.

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Members

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Investigators

- [Dr Josep Maria Haro](#)
Parc Sanitari Sant Joan de Déu

Contacts

- [Dr Josep Maria Haro](#)
Parc Sanitari Sant Joan de Déu

General Information

Year created	2015
Types of cohorts	• Population cohort
Countries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cuba • Mexico • Dominican Republic • Puerto Rico • China • Peru • India • Venezuela • Austria • Australia • Greece • Spain • Finland • Poland • United Kingdom • Russian • Lithuania • Czech Republic • United States of America • Japan • Ghana • Netherlands • South Korea • South Africa • Denmark • Hungary • Sweden • Switzerland • Ireland • Estonia • Belgium • Israel • Slovenia

Methodology for harmonization and integration

Strategy of harmonization	ex-post
Type of harmonization	Retrospective
Supplementary information	A platform of free software applications, developed by Maelstrom Research, is used to store the original datasets, guide the harmonization process and create a web portal for the studies from the ATHLOS Consortium, as well as the final harmonized databases. UBCoS is the only study that harmonized data is kept in their institution.
Number of cohorts	
Total	18
With harmonized data	18
Will more cohorts be harmonized?	✓
Number of harmonized variables (max.)	180
Analyses	
Software	Specific software
Analyses	• Pooled analyses
Data processing methods	Algorithmic
Access	
Availability of metadata	✓
Availability of individual data	Under request

- Croatia
- Luxembourg
- Portugal
- France
- Germany
- Italy

Setting International

Funding European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme

Criteria of cohort's to be included Each study includes one or more populations and provides data on health determinants and age-related events.

Participants	
Number of participants	
Total	411,000
With harmonized data	411,000
Age range of the samples	
Minimum age	18
Maximum age	120

Individual Studies				
Acronym	Name	Study design	Participants	Countries
10/66	The 10/66 Dementia Research Group Population-Based Cohort Study	Population cohort	15,901	Cuba , India , China , Peru , Mexico , Puerto Rico , Dominican Republic , Venezuela
ALSA	Australian Longitudinal Study of Aging	Population cohort	2,087	Australia
ATTICA	The ATTICA Study	Population cohort	3,042	Greece
CHARLS	The China Health and Retirement Longitudinal Study	Population cohort	17,708	China
COURAGE	Collaborative Research on Ageing in Europe	Population cohort	10,800	Finland , Poland , Spain
ELSA	English Longitudinal Study of Ageing	Population cohort	12,099	United Kingdom
ENRICA	Seniors-ENRICA	Population cohort	2,614	Spain
H2000/11	Health 2000/2011	Population cohort	22,261	Finland
HAPIEE	The Health, Alcohol and Psychosocial factors in Eastern Europe Study	Population cohort	36,106	Czech Republic , Poland , Russian , Lithuania
HRS	Health and Retirement Survey	Population cohort	37,317	United States of America

Figure 17. Example of the public data content from an initiative.

2.6 Repository search

The green button “Search” at the top menu opens the general search page.

Fields are described in Mica defining a taxonomy which is then used in the search page.

The search can be led by selecting or writing the desired initiative/study properties through the left menu of the general search page.

Figure 18. Search page for initiatives.

Figure 19. Search page for studies.

3. NEXT STEPS

The repository has already been launched and progressively will be completed with all data collected about initiatives and their studies. To achieve this aim, we are exhaustively working on verifying each initiative with their IPs. This is a laborious but necessary step to offer high-quality content for the repository.

This process will take some months due to difficulties in receiving feedback from all IPs to corroborate the found information and to get permission to publish all the data in a public repository.

Therefore, the repository will continue to be updated during the next months.

